

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF CHEMICAL INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *In this article, the composition of the management system of enterprises, management technology, factors necessary for the effectiveness of the management system, a mechanism for continuous improvement of the system are proposed and recommendations are developed.*

Keywords: *efficiency, management system, management technology, functional structures, risk management, modern management, quality management.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯМИ ХИМИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье предложены состав системы управления предприятиями, технология управления, факторы, необходимые для эффективности системы управления, механизм постоянного совершенствования системы и разработаны рекомендации.*

Ключевые слова: *эффективность, система управления, технология управления, функциональные структуры, управление рисками, современный менеджмент, управление качеством.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of the chemical industry is of great importance in improving the living conditions of the population in the world. "As a result of applying modern management approaches to chemical industry enterprises, in 2021, the volume of production of chemical products in the world increased by 6.1%, of which 3.1% in developed countries and 7.2% in developing countries". Today, improving the management system of enterprises in the development of the chemical industry and ensuring its competitiveness is one of the urgent issues.

In the conditions of modern market relations, the active development of industrial sectors, the production of competitive products, and the organization of a management system flexible to the changing environment are of great importance. Today, it is required to create corporate forms of management, to change management methods and styles of managers, and to digitize activities in the management system.

In recent years, in Uzbekistan, the strategic development of chemical industry enterprises, the development of a management system flexible to the external environment, and the implementation of large-scale transformation processes in the field are being carried out. Also, it is important to use a management model that allows for timely, quick and effective development of management decisions in modern industrial structures. In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, priorities are set for "the development of the chemical and gas-chemical industries and the production of products worth 2 billion US dollars in the chemical industry by increasing the level of natural gas processing from 8% to 20%." It is necessary to improve the management systems of enterprises in the effective implementation of these priority tasks.

Literature analysis

Development and development of business management models in industrial enterprises G. Hamel, K. Prahalad, G. Booch, J. Rumbaugh, I. Jacobson, C. Burmester, D. Luttgens, F. Piller, M. Rappa, B. Mahadevan, It was studied by scientists such as A. Afuah, C. Tucci.

General problems of business management models in industrial enterprises are reflected in the scientific works of V. Kotelnikov, G. Chesboro, B. Kovalenko, K. Amangeldiev, E. Moreva, O. Tretyak, D. Klimanov and others from the CIS.

However, no separate research work has been carried out on the development of business management models, the procedure and mechanism of their application to industrial enterprises. This situation requires the need to conduct scientific research on this topic and determines the relevance of the research direction.

Methodology used

The methodological basis of the research was general scientific methods and special techniques for analyzing the economic situation of enterprises. Scientific categories such as "efficiency", "enterprise management", "planning" and "enterprise management strategy" are understood and applied. The results of the activities of other scientists involved in the development of tools for managing chemical enterprises and improving their efficiency, statistical reports of enterprises, and development of regulatory documents were used.

The main part

The enterprise management system includes management relations related to rational decision-making, organization of information flow, planning and implementation of work based on certain principles.

Enterprise management system can be divided into three areas:

- Providing information on the processes of developing and implementing solutions to problems;
- Development of standards and procedures for solving tasks;
- Employee motivation system.

The management system of the enterprise is a set of processes for regulating processes and events at all levels, ensuring the interaction of subsystems, and achieving the enterprise's goal. Enterprise management subsystem can be divided into methodology, process, structure and management technology types.

In this, the management methodology includes the main purpose and tasks, principles, laws and legalities, functions and methods of managing the enterprise.

The management process includes the communication system, management technology, i.e. making and implementing management decisions, information supply in the enterprise.

Figure 1. The composition of the enterprise management system.

The management structure includes the functional and organizational structure, the model of organizational relations, the specific structure of the relations of the top management bodies, and the provision of personnel. And management technology organizes organizational technologies, communication channels, document management system.

In turn, management methodology and process includes management activity, structure, technique and mechanism. The condition of the elements of the enterprise's management system directly affects the efficiency of its entire operation.

The management system of industrial enterprises is a tool that supports the successful operation of this enterprise. In the development of the management system of industrial enterprises, a specialist needs skills such as thorough knowledge of the enterprise, creative thinking, and the creation of a development strategy.

Thus, it is important to review the management system of enterprises in solving their problems. In the conditions of market relations, it is necessary to organize business activities on the basis of modern management principles that allow the rational use of all types of resources in order for the enterprise to achieve the set goal to the maximum extent.

The main principle of the management system should be to produce products on time and to a certain standard, reduce costs and increase the competitiveness of the enterprise.

Figure 1.2. A set of factors necessary for the effectiveness of the management system

As a result of a deep study of the modern management system, it can be said that the standards used in production, quality management, performance indicators, and information related to development can be shown as necessary factors for the effectiveness of the management system.

Also, rational planning of resources serves as the main criterion for increasing the efficiency of the management system. Determining the level of optimal use of funds, fixed assets, and workers is a very important factor. Today, it is important to organize production with effective use of labor, raw materials, financial and information resources.

To increase the competitiveness of the enterprise, it is necessary to develop a business plan and work towards a specific goal. For the continuous development of business, it is necessary to work on strategies and organize work within the framework of a specific mechanism. At the same time, the enterprise is required to monitor and analyze itself at the end of a certain period.

Currently, it is appropriate to use different approaches in the management of industrial enterprises. Using the methodology of a systematic target approach ensures the selection of two main groups of factors that influence the formation and development of organizational structures of enterprise management. These include the structure that reflects the characteristics of enterprises and the influence of the external environment.

In the era of global changes, constant changes in the external environment, modernization of technologies have different effects on the general state of the enterprise. Today, there are many problems in the management of large enterprises, including the dissatisfaction of middle managers with work activities, the existence of costs associated with various district control systems, and the decrease in the volume of production.

Therefore, the structural restructuring of production and, first of all, its management system is becoming an increasingly urgent task, in order to solve it, it is appropriate to apply the systematic principles of modern management to create an effective organizational and economic model of enterprise management.

When developing a mechanism for continuous improvement of the management system of industrial enterprises, it is necessary to create a system consisting of a number of interrelated elements. That is, the combination of measurement, analysis, development, control and evaluation functions plays an important role in enterprise management. All these elements should serve to support the overall goal of the system.

Figure 1.3. Continuous improvement cycle of management system

When making decisions on improving the management system, it is important to consider the company's values and existing opportunities, to increase responsibility and accountability, to create a comfortable environment for employees, to provide additional opportunities, and to create conditions for increasing their skills and experience.

It is also necessary to evaluate and analyze the company's activities in order to prevent the risks that can be observed in the management system. In order to prevent risks, it is necessary to carry out activities such as effective organization of personnel management, ensuring the safety of equipment, constant analysis of the market environment, evaluation of competitors' behavior, and forecasting.

It is known that analysis of the management process, development strategy development, control, evaluation, and cycle time measurement are among the most important tasks. In the analysis of the management process, methods such as research of financial indicators, expert evaluation of the management system, SWOT, PEST, GAP can be used. In developing the system, it is necessary to develop a strategy and improve activities based on a clear mechanism. In order to study the implementation of plans or the state of implementation of works, control and evaluation works are carried out in the management.

Conclusions and suggestions

During the research, the following conclusions and proposals were developed:

- The management system of the enterprise is the integration of interrelated systems that serve to ensure the competitiveness of the enterprise.

- As a result of applying a modern management system to the chemical industry enterprises, the enterprise organizes a management system based on a clear strategic direction, the functional tasks of all managers and employees are clarified, the market value of the enterprise increases, brand strategy management, investment attractiveness is achieved, and the depressing chemical industry enterprises gain competitive advantage. a clear mission to fight is developed, internal and external environmental factors of enterprises are analytically studied, specific measures to prevent losses in business are developed.

- Optimization of chemical industry enterprises serves to increase economic efficiency, create the most optimal management system, and get out of a crisis situation.

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